

A STUDY OF THE CARBYLAMINE REACTION

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Carbylamine, produced in ethyl alcohol solution from various amino compounds under identical conditions, has been estimated by hydrolysing it to formic acid. The amount formed does not exceed 35% of the theoretical value and decreases considerably on dilution of the reaction mixture. Substitution of +I groups in aniline increases the yield whereas -I groups diminish it. In the mixture of iodoform and aniline, the reaction is induced photochemically in the absence of alkali. Urea has also been found to afford an isonitrile.

There being no reference in literature to kinetics or even a quantitative treatment of often-used carbylamine reaction, it was felt that such a study might be fruitful. On allowing to react an alcoholic solution of potassium hydroxide with that of chloroform at 40° and determining the rate of disappearance of alkali acidimetrically, it was found that the rate remained practically unaltered by adding aniline to the reaction mixture. It appeared that the first step in the carbylamine reaction was the hydrolysis of chloroform and an intermediary, formed thereby, attacked the amine. As the nature and concentration of the intermediary was not known, a kinetic study was found impracticable. Hence, a quantitative study was undertaken in which carbylamine, produced under varying conditions of temperature and concentration of the reactants, was estimated. In all the experiments excess of chloroform was used and the reaction was carried out to complete consumption of the alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

Evaluation of Carbylamine.—This was done by hydrolysing it in presence of dilute sulphuric acid and estimating the formic acid produced.

Carbylamine was prepared mostly by treating in a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask 3.5*N*-KOH (1 c.c.) with 0.4*M* amine solution (2 c.c.) and 40% CHCl₃ solution (1 c.c.) in EtOH at 56° for 3 hours during which time all the KOH was consumed. The flask was well stoppered during heating with a good compressed wood cork which was placed in position with a little pressure. For estimating carbylamine, the contents of the flask were cooled to 0° by placing it in crushed ice and then 25 c.c. of 0.1*N*-H₂SO₄ was pipetted into it with a fast pipette, the cork being lifted as little as possible. The acidified solution was again stoppered and heated at 56° for 8 hrs. In a few cases the cork yielded to the gas pressure inside, which necessitated repetition of the experiment. Later the contents were cooled to room temperature and titrated with 0.04*N*-NaOH solution, using phenolphthalein as indicator. A blank was carried out in an identical manner except for the addition of the amine solution, instead of which 2 c.c. of EtOH was used. In case of aniline, the values obtained for carbylamine were verified by estimating the residual aniline. After the formation of carbylamine, the contents of the flask were diluted with 25 c.c. of EtOH and boiled for about 10 minutes to drive off

all the carbylamine, as judged by its foul odour. An aliquot of the solution was then acidified with strong HCl solution and evaporated on a water-bath to a small bulk. The aniline hydrochloride remaining as residue was estimated by the bromine method (Stone, "Determination of Organic Compounds", 1956, p. 180). In Table I the values for carbylamine experimentally found are compared with those calculated from the aniline used up.

TABLE I

Estimation of carbylamine by acid hydrolysis.(2 c.c. of 0.4M aniline soln. + 1 c.c. of KOH + 1 c.c. of 40% CHCl₃)

Normality of KOH soln.	3.5 N	3.0 N	2.7 N	2.5 N
Carbylamine found (c.c. of 0.04M soln.).	7.1	6.0	5.2	4.7
„ calc.	7.0	6.0	5.3	4.6

In cases of strong bases like methyl, ethyl and benzyl amines, the evaluation of carbylamine was done indirectly by titrating the remaining base with 0.1N-H₂SO₄ in presence of phenol red. A blank was carried out by heating the same volume of the solution of the base under identical conditions.

Effect of Dilution.—The formation of carbylamine from aniline was studied by treating 2 c.c. of 0.4M aniline solution with 1 c.c. of 2.9N-KOH and 1 c.c. of 40% CHCl₃ solution. The reaction mixture was diluted with varying quantities of alcohol, and heated at 56° till all the KOH was used up. The carbylamine produced diminished with dilution, as shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Alcohol added (c.c.) for dilution	...	Nil	4	8	16
Carbylamine produced (c.c. of 0.04M soln.)	...	5.7	3.5	2.4	1.2

Effect of Concentrations of Aniline and KOH.—The reaction was first carried out by keeping the aniline concentration constant and changing that of the alkali. Later the aniline concentration alone was altered. Heating was carried out at 56° till the KOH was completely consumed. The results recorded in Table III reveal that the carbylamine produced increases with the increase in concentration of aniline and KOH, both.

TABLE III

(2 c.c. of aniline + 1 c.c. of KOH + 1 c.c. of 40% CHCl₃)

Conc. {	Aniline (M)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1
	KOH (N)	0.8	1.8	2.6	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Carbylamine produced (c.c. of 0.04M soln.)	1.3	2.8	4.8	7.0	4.0	2.5	1.8

Effect of Temperature.—The same concentrations of the amine, alkali and CHCl₃ were used for the reactions at 25°, 40° and 56°, and the time allowed for the reaction was 240, 50 and 3 hours respectively, when all the alkali was used up. The carbylamine produced was found to decrease slightly with increase in temperature, as shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

(2 c.c. of 0.4M amine soln. + 1 c.c. of 3.5N-KOH + 1 c.c. of 40% CHCl₃)

Temp.	Carbylamine produced (c.c. of 0.04M soln.)			
	Aniline.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine.
25°	7.9	8.2	7.4	6.8
40°	7.4	7.6	7.2	6.4
56°	7.1	7.4	7.0	5.2

Effect of Substitution.—Various substituted anilines and other amines were taken and carbylamine, produced under identical conditions, was estimated. The method adopted is comparable with the "Competition method", described by Ingold ("Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", 1953, p. 245) in connection with the action of HNO₃ on benzene and toluene. All the reactions were carried out at 56° and the time allowed was 3 hrs. In Table V the carbylamine produced has been given along with the strength of the base, expressed in terms of the Lowry-Brønsted system, as reported by Badger ("Structure and Reactions of Aromatic Compounds", 1954, p. 76, 196). The term $pK_a = -\log K_a$, where K_a is the acid dissociation constant of the base.

TABLE V

Heated at 56° for 3 hours. Other conditions same as in Table IV.

Base.	pK_a .	Carbylamine produced (c.c. of 0.04M soln.).	Base.	pK_a .	Carbylamine produced (c.c. of 0.04M soln.).
Aniline	4.6	7.1	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	4.5	7.4
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	2.8	4.7	<i>m</i> - "	4.2	7.4
<i>m</i> - "	2.1	5.6	<i>p</i> - "	5.3	8.4
<i>p</i> - "	3.5	5.8			
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	-0.2	2.7	α -Naphthol	4.0	3.7
<i>m</i> - "	2.6	4.7	β -Naphthol	4.3	5.4
<i>p</i> - "	1.1	2.7	Benzyl amine	9.4	7.5
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	4.4	5.2			
<i>m</i> - "	4.7	7.0	Methyl "	10.7	7.6
<i>p</i> - "	5.1	7.4	Ethyl "	10.7	7.4

Induced Photochemical Reaction.—It was felt that by extracting the halogen atoms from a methyl trihalide, an intermediary was produced which reacted with an amine to form carbylamine. Instead of alkali, this extraction could be carried out photochemically as well, in presence of O₂. A benzene solution of CHI₃ in the presence of sunlight and O₂ was found to decompose completely into free I₂ and an unknown product. When dilute solutions were taken (0.1–0.05%) the iodine obtained was quantitative, but in case of stronger solutions iodine liberated gave a deep red or violet colour to the solution which acted as an "autofilter" and prevented further

action of light. This difficulty was overcome by adding aqueous solution of hypo to the benzene solution and shaking the mixture occasionally. This photochemical oxidation was found to take place in all organic solvents, but in case of benzene and ether it was comparatively rapid. The unknown product, formed after extracting all the I_2 photochemically from CHI_3 , was found to produce carbylamine in the presence of an amine. A strong solution of CHI_3 (10 c.c.) in benzene, taken in a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask, was treated with 0.2N hypo solution (10 c.c.) and 4 drops of aniline. The mixture was exposed to sunlight with occasional shaking. The O_2 enclosed in the flask was sufficient for the photo-oxidation and in about 15 minutes a distinct smell of carbylamine was obtained. The reaction took place in the absence of hypo solution as well, but the smell of carbylamine obtained was very faint. Toluidines, when similarly treated, also gave carbylamine.

D I S C U S S I O N

Vorländer and Guthke (*Ber.*, 1929, **62B**, 549) reported that an alcoholic solution containing $CHCl_3$ and KOH possessed a strong reducing power which could not be accounted for by the mere presence of $H.COOH$, formed during the reaction. They postulated the formation of $HO.CHO$ (hydroxyformaldehyde), an aldehydic isomer of $H.COOH$, as an intermediate product and also claimed to have precipitated it with methone. Hine (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2438) has presented a strong case in favour of the view that CCl_2 is produced as an intermediary. The formation of a highly reactive compound like activated CO, $HO.CHO$ or CCl_2 is undeniable. This intermediate compound attacks the amine :

As shown above, there are two competing reactions taking place. These seem to possess different temperature coefficients and molecularity, because the yield of carbylamine varies with temperature and dilution.

The quantity of carbylamine produced was found to depend upon the basic strength of the amine (Table V). The basic property of the NH_2 gr. up is associated with the lone pair of electrons available on the nitrogen for forming the bond with the proton (Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 1952, p. 206). The formation of carbylamine also seems to depend on the availability of this lone pair of electrons. Negative substituents (Cl and NO_2) in aniline produce a mesomeric effect which attracts this lone pair of electrons towards the $-I$ group and consequently diminishes the yield of carbylamine. The NO_2 group leads to a preferential diminution of electron density at *ortho* and *para* positions (Badger, *loc. cit.*, p. 199). Therefore *ortho*- and *para*-nitroanilines should furnish a poorer yield of carbylamine than the *meta*-isomer. This fact has been borne out experimentally (Table V). Very similar considerations apply to the positive substituents which generally release electrons and increase the yield.

A *meta*-methoxy group is base-weakening whereas *para*-methoxy is base-strengthening (Badger, *loc. cit.*, p. 204) ; hence, the yield of carbylamine should be more in *p*-anisidine, as already found. The effect of methyl substituent also is more marked in the

para position because in this position the mesomeric and inductive effects reinforce one another and increase the electron density. The highest yield of carbylamine among the toluidines was from the *para* compound.

The carbylamine reaction is not afforded by the amides, because the lone pair of electrons belonging to the nitrogen atom shifts towards the carbon and from there to the oxygen atom (Pauling, *loc. cit.*, p. 133). This electron displacement causes weakening of the basic strength of the NH_2 group. It would therefore appear that wherever there is a lone pair of electrons available on the nitrogen atom (in NH_2 group), carbylamine reaction must take place. Urea possesses slightly basic properties, because the electrons of one of the two NH_2 groups shift towards the carbon atom, but the same is not true of the other group. Hence, urea should also form carbylamine. This fact was experimentally verified and positive results were obtained. When urea (10 g.) was heated with 3.4*N* alcoholic KOH (5 c.c.) and 25% CHCl_3 solution (5 c.c.), a highly toxic gas with a foul odour, like aliphatic carbylamines, was evolved.

The photochemically induced reaction can be explained on the assumption that CHI_3 on photo-oxidation in sunlight produces free I_2 and an active isomer of CO which reacts with an amine to give carbylamine. Emschwiller (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1939, *v.* 6, 561) reported that equal volumes of CO and CO_2 were produced along with free I_2 during the photo-oxidation. An attempt to isolate the unknown carbon compound produced, by extracting it with ether, failed as the same appeared to be gaseous.

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